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QUESTIONNAIRE

Date

Unit name	Alte University
Country	Georgia
Number of researchers	Up to 500
Number of students	2502
Link to the website	Homepage - Alte University
Characteristics of research activities (max. 300 words)	<p>Based on its mission, Alte University creates an "academic space where knowledge acquisition, sharing and creation of new knowledge is carried out through applied research, innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration". The goal of the university is to develop research products that are valuable for development in technological, economic and other innovative directions, to integrate these results into the educational process.</p> <p>In accordance with the strategic development plan, Alte University's three-year action plan includes the implementation of projects focused on applied research, interdisciplinary research and involvement in internationally recognized research collaborations. University schools offer specialized courses to students, such as research methods and academic writing, which build fundamental research skills and prepare students for research activities. Research-based learning modules involve students working on small-scale research projects, ensuring that not only theoretical concepts are taught, but practical experience is gained.</p> <p>Both students and academic staff are involved in the research carried out at Alte University, which contributes to their professional development and enhancement of research skills.</p> <p>The university constantly cares about the development of research activities, for which the share of the allocated budget was determined at 3% of the total budget. The constant growth of the mentioned budget over the years emphasizes the perception of the importance of the development of research activities by the university.</p>

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	<p>Accordingly, the research activity of Alte University is characterized by its strong emphasis on interdisciplinary cooperation and the practical application of research results. Future plans include increasing the number of research publications, strengthening cooperation with international partners, and supporting interdisciplinary research.</p>
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Does your institution have a formal system for assessing researchers?

Yes

No

If so:

	What document (Rector's ordinance, Senate resolution, national regulations) regulates the researchers assessment system?
1.	<p>Rule for Planning, Implementing and Evaluating the Scientific-Research Component (approved by the board of directors).</p> <p>From QA – “QA mechanisms” (approved by the board of directors)</p> <p>P.S. Funding Rule for the Scientific and Research Activities of Alte University Academic Staff (approved by the board of directors);</p>
2.	What time frame of work is taken into account in the assessment?
	Once in an academic year by Research Department & Quality Assessment Department.
3.	What are the basic assessment criteria?
	<p>Criteria by R&P D: Bibliometric Indicator Components – Productivity (number of publications within a defined period, by type of publication: textbook, monograph, article, etc.); number of publications in peer-reviewed journals; number of publications in international journals; number of publications in international journals with an impact factor; citation index, which indicates the significance of the work (where applicable); co-authorship with foreign scientists, which reflects international cooperation.</p> <p>Staff Indicator Components – Number of affiliated staff with an academic degree; membership of academic staff in scientific councils and/or scientific professional associations; participation of academic staff in conferences/symposiums, seminars, workshops (including international) and other events, and the form of participation; scientific grants obtained by academic staff; supervision of master's theses and the number of such theses (including the number of theses awarded the highest grades out of the total number); academic staff's editorial/reviewing activities.</p>

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	<p>Financial Indicator Components – Financial expenditures on science and the existing material and technical resources.</p> <p>Criteria for the exact project: Relevance of the topic, innovativeness, appropriateness of the research method to the research question, interdisciplinarity of the research, applied value of the research, potential for commercialization and sustainability, collaboration with international partners, experience of the research team, consideration of ethical principles of research, and alignment of the budget with the proposal.</p> <p>Criteria by QAD: Annual evaluation of research activities, which, in addition to assessing the activities carried out, also includes the evaluation of compliance with academic integrity, taking into account the results of its monitoring. For the evaluation, the university uses research productivity data such as: the number of publications during the year and their quality; citation analysis of publications; collaborative initiatives/projects in the field of research both within and outside the university; and the level of involvement of lecturers and students in scientific-research activities. The evaluation will also consider the financial resources allocated by the university for research and the rate of attracting external funding sources. As for the evaluation of compliance with academic integrity, the university analyzes the number of participants (students and staff) in academic integrity trainings, uses participant feedback on the effectiveness of these training programs, analyzes data on violations of academic integrity principles (including plagiarism) and the effectiveness of responses to such cases, and conducts focus groups with students and staff to explore more deeply their perceptions and understanding of academic integrity.</p>
4.	<p>Do the criteria or their importance differ for job groups (assistant/assistant professor/professor) and/or scientific disciplines?</p> <p>They are the same.</p>
5.	<p>How are researchers informed about the assessment system and rules?</p> <p>Via web page, email and face-to-face meetings.</p>
6.	<p>Do scientists have an influence on determining the principles of assessment?</p> <p>Yes, the draft version of the document was shared with them while elaborating and their positions were considered.</p>
7.	<p>Do they receive feedback after the assessment (in what form – written/oral)?</p> <p>Yes, from QAD by an annual report published on university web page.</p>
8.	<p>Do you use electronic tools to assess scientific achievements?</p> <p>Scientific databases, Journals, One drive, Turnitin.</p>
9.	<p>Are there any automated elements in the assessment system, e.g. is there a possibility to generate achievements report from the employee portal?</p> <p>No. Staff performance evaluation platform will be implemented within one year and it will cover this function.</p>
10.	<p>Does the assessment of scientific achievements consider bibliometric indicators??</p> <p>Yes, ex.: number and types of publications, citations received, journal impact factors, h-index, co-authorship...</p>

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	Do the assessment criteria consider elements considered as Open Science?
11.	Funded research project details are published on university's web page. Peer review is transparent. Public engagement is ensured within scientific research activities.
	How often is the assessment system changed or modified and for what reason (legislative changes or under the influence of opinions?)
12.	During the last decade, it was changed once, as the university owners and strategic plan changed. According to the new policy - Rule for Planning, Implementing, and Evaluating the Scientific-Research Component, it is considered to review the document with the involvement of stakeholders in every three years.
	Is the result of the assessment associated with a promotion, contract extension or other element, such as a salary increase?
13.	Yes. Mostly in terms of contract extension.
	Are the criteria for scientific assessment related to the implementation of the university's strategy/vision/mission?
14.	Yes. Ex.: Extract from university mission – “We are dedicated to cultivating a vibrant academic community where knowledge is discovered and shared through applied research, innovation, and interdisciplinary collaborations.” Assessment criteria – “Relevance of the topic, innovativeness, collaboration with international partners”
	Are the most prestigious ERC grants particularly recognized and promoted in the assessment of scientific activity?
15.	Yes. Evaluation criteria - “scientific grants obtained by the staff”.

If no:

1.	What does the assessment process for researchers look like?
2.	What are the assessment rules?
3.	Despite the lack of a formal system, do researchers know the principles of assessment?
4.	Are there any consequences after the assessment of academic staff are completed, and if so, what are they?
5.	Do you intend to implement a formal system for assessing scientists in the future?

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P.S. RD support:

- Advancement of staff research activities, encouraging their participation in research projects, conferences, seminars, and workshops.
- Internal financial backing for research initiatives aimed at enhancing knowledge in priority research areas of the university, funding various initiatives, including research projects, conference attendance, publication of articles in scientific journals, and hosting seminars and workshops.
- Fostering international research collaborations and partnerships with other higher education and research institutions.
- Provision of both financial and logistical assistance to faculty and students for their involvement in international and local conferences and forums.